

EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES DIRECTED TO THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' COMPETENCES

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Abstract. *In this article, opinions and recommendations are given about the processes related to the formation of competencies in students during the educational process, the use of educational technologies in the course of the lesson, the importance and relevance of organization based on the competence approach, and the implementation of its specific features in the educational system of our country.*

Keywords: *competence, types of competence, competence approach, base, general, professional competences, educational standards, qualification requirements, assessment criteria.*

The Law "On Education", the National Model of Personnel Training from the "National Program of Personnel Training", Decision No. 187 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2017 ("On Approval of State Educational Standards of General Secondary and Secondary Special Vocational Education") the tasks arising from the continuous education system require large-scale research in order to increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

The study of best practices in the educational system of the developed countries of the world showed the need to implement a competent approach to the continuous education process.

Implementation of the following tasks by implementing a competent approach to the continuous education process:

- In order to meet the social needs of our country for young people who are able to solve the problems of society, science, production and independent life of the individual in the future, to teach students to creatively apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in new unexpected situations;

- Satisfy the needs of students to learn the basics of science, develop their interests, and build personal qualities during learning the content of education by creating problem learning situations;

- By focusing the educational activities of students on specific objects and teaching them to solve existing problems, achieving the mastery of creative activity experiences by students along with the formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications standardized by standards of country education;

- To guide students to the profession by increasing their readiness for specific practical activities, to the field of science as a result of the development of creative activity experiences;

- It is possible to prepare students for an independent life by applying the scientific and theoretical knowledge acquired from the subjects in practice in concrete and processual problem situations.

The main essence of teaching based on the competence approach is to direct the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by the students in the educational process organized by subjects to the formation of competencies to use in their personal life, as well as in their professional and social activities in the future.

Pupils should have the basic competencies necessary to engage in personal, social, economic and professional relationships in the future, to take their place in society, to solve the problems encountered in this process, and most importantly, to be competitive in their field and profession.

It is known that, through the educational process, pupils acquire basic competencies, including communicative, informational skills, self-development competence as a person, socially active citizenship competence, general cultural competences, mathematical literacy, awareness and use of science and technology innovations.

A competent approach to the educational process is a set of general principles that allow the organization of the educational process on the basis of innovative technologies and the analysis of the results of the enrichment of the educational content in order to achieve the educational goals.

Among them, it is necessary to consider the following:

- To develop the ability of students to solve problems in various activities and areas of independent life based on knowledge, skills and abilities, their own life experiences, observations, personal conclusions, to perform activities required in problematic situations in accordance with the purpose;

- To increase students' interest in the selection of educational content and to create methodological support, to expand their scientific worldview, to solve moral, ideological-political, educational-educational problems, to apply didactically processed knowledge, skills and qualifications of students in new unexpected situations, their own life experiences, paying attention to the existence of educational tasks that allow drawing scientific conclusions based on their observations;

- The main goal in the organization of the educational process is to create conditions for students to acquire knowledge, skills, qualifications standardized by DTS, as well as to work with information, to acquire communicative skills, to acquire mathematical literacy, to have social activity, to acquire experiences related to independent solving of educational problems;

- Evaluating the results of the educational process based on the results achieved at a certain stage of this process, that is, the level of knowledge, skills and competences acquired by students, which are the basis of competence;

- In a competent approach, the goals of teaching are to aim at such priorities as students' self-understanding, understanding of the ways to achieve educational goals in the educational process, activation of students' educational and cognitive activities, adaptation of students to society and independent life through self-development, and socialization.

Competence is divided into degrees according to the methods of formation and importance in a person's life.

Competencies that prepare the possibilities for the general development of a student are called basic competence, and competences that are formed only through the subject of study are called special competences.

The analysis of the literature showed that the students' competencies are divided into three levels: 1. Basic competencies are the competencies that are formed through the content and teaching process of all subjects included in the curriculum.

2. General (subject) competences - the competences formed by the implementation of interdisciplinary connections in the teaching of social-humanitarian, natural-mathematical and practical subjects included in the curriculum are taken into account.

3. Special competences are the competences that are formed on the basis of knowledge, skills and qualifications in the educational process.

Competence of the student is the ability to use and apply in practice the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students in solving practical and theoretical problems encountered in their daily life.

In order to develop the above-mentioned basic competencies in students, it is necessary to analyze and analyze the content of the academic subject, to design all forms of teaching: lessons, extracurricular activities, excursions, and activities outside the group.

Below, we will consider the possibilities of forming basic competencies in students in the teaching of subjects.

With the aim of developing communicative competence, teachers should master oral and written speech in all classes, which will be necessary for students to communicate in society in the future for creating an opportunity to write answers, to follow the norms of behavior culture in communication with peers and teachers, to be able to express one's opinion while respecting the opinion of group members while working in small groups, to be able to work in team cooperation, to be able to defend and convince one's opinion based on acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications, to manage one's passions in educational debates organized in classes and in various conflict situations, to be able to make decisions necessary to solve problems and disagreements, to master foreign languages in addition to one's native language.

The following educational work skills, standardized by country standards of education, are the basis for students' communicative competence: Skills for working with educational literature:

- Knowing and applying the instructions given in the introduction of educational literature;
- Being able to distinguish phrases separated by color;
- Targeting based on the content of educational literature;
- Knowing and using symbols and base signals;
- Knowing how to use footers;
- Being able to use instructions. Skills for working on the text:
- Being able to make a plan for the read text;
- Finding answers to questions using the text;
- Writing a lecture using the text;
- Being able to perform tasks of a practical nature using the text of the textbook;
- Being able to make tables, diagrams, schemes using the text of the textbook;
- Being able to find concepts and rules using the text of the textbook;
- Making a description of the object, making a conclusion.

It is recommended to use innovative technologies in the teaching process in order to acquire the above-mentioned educational work skills in the students.

It should be noted that in training sessions, didactic game technology includes conference, press conference, game exercises, cooperative learning technology, working in small groups, group teaching, "Arra" or "Zigzag", "Let's study together" methods, problem-based educational technology "Brainstorming", Through the use of "case-study" methods, students have the opportunity to develop communicative competence while acquiring knowledge, skills and competencies.

Various lessons, extracurricular activities, excursions, and extracurricular activities play an important role in the formation of socially active civic competence in students during the course

of teaching subjects. In this process, students are introduced to the events, events and processes in nature and society, the articles of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the subject, pay attention to mental, spiritual-ethical, economic, legal, physical, labor education, contribute to the development of the Motherland by mastering a particular profession, society and it is necessary to serve for the interests of the family, to show kindness to people, to encourage them to be generous.

All forms of education: lessons, extracurricular activities, excursions, and extracurricular activities play an important role in the formation of socially active civic competence in students.

Nature conservation nights, greening events, meetings with famous writers and scientists prepare the opportunity for students to develop socially active citizenship competence.

In order to build universal competences in students, in the teaching of teacher subjects, by instilling national and universal human values into the minds and hearts of students, respecting the worldview, religious beliefs, national and ethnic characteristics, traditions and ceremonies of others, carefully preserving the historical, spiritual and cultural heritage of the people, established in the society. It is necessary to observe the rules of etiquette, to dress properly, to follow cultural norms and a healthy lifestyle while walking, to pay attention to intellectual, spiritual-moral, economic, legal, physical, labor education, as well as aesthetic education.

Thematic evenings, events, meetings, and Saturdays held with students play an important role in the formation of general cultural competences in students.

In order to develop students' mathematical literacy, knowledge of science and technology innovations, and the ability to use them, the teacher should start working with various calculation problems and non-standard educational tasks in order to develop students' independent and creative thinking skills.

Teachers should pay attention to the formation of general (subject) competences in students along with formation of basic competencies. In the process of education, the teacher should start designing the process of learning the above-mentioned competencies in each subject, and determine the basic, general and private competencies that are composed based on the knowledge, skills and abilities of the content of this subject, and these issues should find their expression in the technological map of the lesson.

Educational goals formed on the basis of advanced pedagogical technologies play an important role in the formation of general and subject-specific competencies in students. It is necessary to form educational goals based on advanced pedagogical technologies and design lesson plans based on them.

The problem of combining general and subject-specific competences among students makes it necessary to specify the professional pedagogical competences of subject teachers.

In conclusion, the problem of students' composition of competencies is the need of the hour to clarify the professional pedagogical competencies of teachers, to update the content of courses based on the requirements of a competent approach in the process of training and upgrading the skills of pedagogical personnel, and to organize and manage teaching on this basis.

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